

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
GRAPHICAL PASSWORD MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
PROJECT
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CHAPTER 1

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The term “graphical password” refers to a user authentication method where pictorial information is used for validation, instead of an alphanumeric password. This method poses many challenges, such as memo ability (which refers to how easy the password is to remember), usability, and security, since graphical passwords may tend to be visually simple and easily forged. Graphical passwords have become popular due to the proliferation of touch screen devices, in particular smart phones and tablets. The prevalent approaches are based on simple graphical passwords, which can be easily remembered and reproduced by potential attackers. In this work, we study user authentication based on finger -drawn doodles (i.e., free-form gestures or sequences of gestures) and on pseudo signatures, which are simplified versions of the signature drawn with the finger tip. Authentication is based on features extracted from the dynamics of the gesture drawing process (e.g., speed or acceleration). These features contain behavioral biometric information, which has been successfully used for automatic user verification based on handwritten signatures. As a consequence, a potential attacker would have to copy not only what the user draws, but also how the user draws it. Unfortunately, graphical passwords tend to be much simpler than signatures and are not composed, in general, of previously learned or heavily practiced movements. This can lead to a higher intra-user variability (i.e., variations between samples produced by the same person) than in the case of signatures or may cause users to forget part of or the whole graphical password.

A range of approaches for recall-based graphical password authentication have been evaluated using measures including resilience to forgeries, memo ability, user acceptance, error rates and time to enroll. Recall-based authentication can be divided in two categories. Exact- match approaches assume that during authentication, a user produces exactly the same drawing provided

during enrollment. Elastic approaches allow some variability between enrollment and authentication. Graphical password authentication systems can be also divided into static and

dynamic approaches. Static or offline systems use the doodle image for authentication, while dynamic or online systems use time functions extracted from the doodle trajectory.

1.2 EXISTING SYSTEM

Authentication based on passwords is used largely in applications for computer security and privacy. However, human actions such as choosing bad passwords and inputting passwords in an insecure way are regarded as “the weakest link” in the authentication chain. Rather than arbitrary alphanumeric strings, users tend to choose passwords either short or meaningful for easy memorization. With web applications and mobile apps piling up, people can access these applications anytime and anywhere with various devices. This evolution brings great convenience but also increases the probability of exposing passwords to shoulder surfing attacks. Attackers can observe directly or use external recording devices to collect users’ credentials. To overcome this problem, we proposed a novel authentication system Pass Matrix, based on graphical passwords to resist shoulder surfing attacks. With a one-time valid login indicator and circulative horizontal and vertical bars covering the entire scope of pass-images, Pass Matrix offers no hint for attackers to figure out or narrow down the password even they conduct multiple camera-based attacks.

DISADVANTAGES

- Assumed that the server and the client devices in our authentication system are trustworthy.
- Assumed that the surveillance cameras that are not under proper management.

1.3 PROPOSED METHOD

Proposing system uses graphical passwords for authentication purposes. User has to register with the username and password. Then a list of five images will be displayed. User has to select an image. The selection of pixel points on the image for users will vary according to the group, they belong. At the time of login, user can login using the password or image. If the password method is selected, the user has to enter the password. An OTP will be sent to the registered mail id. When the OTP is entered correctly, the user’s home page will be displayed. If the image method is selected, the user has to select an image from the list of five images. After selecting the correct image, the specified number of pixel points should be marked correctly. If this step is correct, the user’s home page is displayed.

ADVANTAGES

- Can't predict accurately when there are five images.
- OTP is used for unique identification.

1.3.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

- Processor : Dual core processor 2.6.0 GHZ
- RAM : 1GB
- Hard disk : 160 GB
- Compact Disk : 650 Mb
- Keyboard : Standard keyboard
- Monitor : 15 inch color monitor

1.3.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

- Front End : JSP
- Back End : SQL Server 2008
- Platform : Windows 7
- IDE : Net beans

FRONT END (JSP):

Java Server Page (JSP) is a technology for controlling the content or appearance of Web pages through the use of servlets, small programs that are specified in the Web page and run on the Web server to modify the Web page before it is sent to the user who requested it. Sun Microsystems, the developer of Java, also refers to the JSP technology as the Servlet application program interface (API). JSP is comparable to Microsoft's Active Server Page (ASP) technology. Whereas a Java Server Page calls a Java program that is executed by the Web server, an Active Server Page contains a script that is interpreted by a script interpreter (such as VBScript or JScript) before the page is sent to the user. Architecturally, JSP may be viewed as a high-level

abstraction of Java servlets. JSPs are translated into servlets at runtime, therefore JSP is a Servlets; each JSP servlet is cached and re-used until the original JSP is modified. JSP can be used independently or as the view component of a server-side model–view–controller design, normally with JavaBeans as the model and Java servlets (or a framework such as Apache Struts) as the controller. This is a type of Model 2 architecture.

JSP allows Java code and certain pre-defined actions to be interleaved with static web markup content, such as HTML, with the resulting page being compiled and executed on the server to deliver a document. The compiled pages, as well as any dependent Java libraries, contain Java byte code rather than machine code. Like any other Java program, they must be executed within a Java virtual machine (JVM) that interacts with the server's host operating system to provide an abstract, platform-neutral environment. JSPs are usually used to deliver HTML and XML documents, but through the use of OutputStream, they can deliver other types of data as well. The Web container creates JSP implicit objects like request, response, session, application, config, page, pageContext, out and exception. JSP Engine creates these objects during translation phase.

SYNTAX

JSP pages use several delimiters for scripting functions. The most basic is `<% ... %>`, which encloses a JSP scriptlet. A scriptlet is a fragment of Java code that is run when the user requests the page. Other common delimiters include `<%= ... %>` for expressions, where the scriptlet and delimiters are replaced with the result of evaluating the expression, and directives, denoted with `<%@ ... %>`. Java code is not required to be complete or self-contained within a single scriptlet block. It can straddle markup content, provided that the page as a whole is syntactically correct. For example, any Java if/for/while blocks opened in one scriptlet must be correctly closed in a later scriptlet for the page to successfully compile. Content which falls inside a split block of Java code (spanning multiple scriptlets) is subject to that code. Content inside an if block will only appear in the output when the if condition evaluates to true. Likewise, content inside a loop construct may appear multiple times in the output, depending upon how many times the loop body runs.

COMPILER

A Java Server Pages compiler is a program that parses JSPs, and transforms them into executable Java Servlets. A program of this type is usually embedded into the application server

and run automatically the first time a JSP is accessed, but pages may also be precompiled for better performance, or compiled as a part of the build process to test for errors. Some JSP containers support configuring how often the container checks JSPs files timestamps to see whether the page has changed. Typically, this timestamp would be set to a short interval (perhaps seconds) during software development, and a longer interval (perhaps minutes, or even never) for a deployed Web application.

5.2 ABOUT MY-SQL

Introduction

MySQL is the world's most used open source relational database management system (RDBMS) as of 2008 that run as a server providing multi-user access to a number of databases. The MySQL development project has made its source code available under the terms of the GNU General Public License, as well as under a variety of proprietary agreements. MySQL was owned and sponsored by a single for-profit firm, the Swedish company MySQL AB, now owned by Oracle Corporation.

MySQL is a popular choice of database for use in web applications, and is a central component of the widely used LAMP open source web application software stack—LAMP is an acronym for "Linux, Apache, MySQL, Perl/PHP/Python." Free-software-open source projects that require a full-featured database management system often use MySQL.

For commercial use, several paid editions are available, and offer additional functionality. Applications which use MySQL databases include: TYPO3, Joomla, Word Press, phpBB, MyBB, Drupal and other software built on the LAMP software stack. MySQL is also used in many high-profile, large-scale World Wide Web products, including Wikipedia, Google (though not for searches), ImagebookTwitter, Flickr, Nokia.com, and YouTube.

Inter Images

MySQL is primarily an RDBMS and ships with no GUI tools to administer MySQL databases or manage data contained within the databases. Users may use the included command line tools, or use MySQL "front-ends", desktop software and web applications that create and manage MySQL databases, build database structures, back up data, inspect status, and work with data records. The official set of MySQL front-end tools, MySQL Workbench is actively developed by Oracle, and is freely available for use.

Graphical

The official MySQL Workbench is a free integrated environment developed by MySQL AB, which enables users to graphically administer MySQL databases and visually design database structures. MySQL Workbench replaces the previous package of software, MySQL GUI Tools. Similar to other third-party packages, but still considered the authoritative MySQL frontend, MySQL Workbench lets users manage database design & modeling, SQL development (replacing MySQL Query Browser) and Database administration (replacing MySQL Administrator). MySQL Workbench is available in two editions, the regular free and open source Community Edition which may be downloaded from the MySQL website, and the proprietary Standard Edition which extends and improves the feature set of the Community Edition.

Command Line

MySQL ships with some command line tools. Third-parties have also developed tools to manage a MySQL server, some listed below. Maatkit - a cross-platform toolkit for MySQL, PostgreSQL and Memcached, developed in Perl Maatkit can be used to prove replication is working correctly, fix corrupted data, automate repetitive tasks, and speed up servers. Maatkit is included with several GNU/Linux distributions such as CentOS and Debian and packages are available for Programming. MySQL works on many different system platforms, including AIX, BSDi, FreeBSD, HP-UX, eComStation, i5/OS, IRIX, Linux, Mac OS X, Microsoft Windows, NetBSD, Novell NetWare, OpenBSD, OpenSolaris, OS/2 Warp, QNX, Solaris, Symbian, SunOS, SCO Open Server, SCO UnixWare, Sanos and Tru64. A port of MySQL to OpenVMS also exists.

MySQL is written in C and C++. Its SQL parser is written in yacc, and a home-brewed lexical analyzer. Many programming languages with language-specific APIs include libraries for accessing MySQL databases. These include MySQL Connector/Net for integration with Microsoft's Visual Studio (languages such as C# and VB are most commonly used) and the JDBC driver for Java. In addition, an ODBC inter image called MyODBC allows additional programming languages that support the ODBC inter image to communicate with a MySQL database, such as ASP or ColdFusion. The HTSQL - URL-based query method also ships with a MySQL adapter, allowing direct interaction between a MySQL database and any web client via structured URLs.

Features

As of April 2009, MySQL offered MySQL 5.1 in two different variants: the open source MySQL Community Server and the commercial Enterprise Server. MySQL 5.5 is offered under the same licenses. They have a common code base and include the following features:

- A broad subset of ANSI SQL 99, as well as extensions
- Cross-platform support
- Stored procedures
- Triggers
- Cursors
- Updatable Views
- Information schema

CHAPTER 2

LOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

2.1 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

A two-dimensional diagram explains how data is processed and transferred in a system. The graphical depiction identifies each source of data and how it interacts with other data sources to reach a common output. Individuals seeking to draft a data flow diagram must identify external inputs and outputs, determine how the inputs and outputs relate to each other, and explain with graphics how these connections relate and what they result in. This type of diagram helps business development and design teams visualize how data is processed and identify or improve certain aspects.

LEVEL 0

DFD Level 0 is also called a Context Diagram. It's a basic overview of the whole system or process being analyzed or modeled. It's designed to be an at-a-glance view, showing the system as a single high-level process, with its relationship to external entities. It should be easily understood by a wide audience, including stakeholders, business analysts, data analysts and developers.

LEVEL 1

DFD Level 1 provides a more detailed breakout of pieces of the Context Level Diagram. You will highlight the main functions carried out by the system, as you break down the high- level process of the Context Diagram into its sub – processes.

2.2 ARCHITECTURAL DIAGRAM

The architecture used in this project is a three tier architecture, which comprises of the presentation tier, logical tier and the data tier. Below is the architecture diagram of the system: Fig 2. System Architecture Registration The users of the system have to firstly register with the application before going ahead and logging into it. The registration consists of firstly choosing the set of images that the user desires for setting the password, out of each those images the user selects the area in the image which least likely guessable. For more security the user also gives a text password which will in turn be hidden in the set of images that the user had selected before this will be done by the concept of image steganography. Image Steganography Image steganography is performed during the registration and login process of the application. It is the process of hiding a data within another. If any type of data such as image, text etc. are hidden within an image, it is known as image steganography. During registration process, a textual password is asked from the user, which is then\

Stored within the images. While the login process, the user is asked to re-enter the password, which will then be compared with the one retrieved from the image. If the retrieved password matches with the one stored during the login process, the user is considered authenticated. Login Process during logging in the user is asked to type the text password which is matched to the text which will be retrieved from the images which was stored during the registration. Along with the text, the images that the user had selected during the registration will be displayed out of which the user will have to click on the same areas that were clicked before.

CHAPTER 3

DATABASE DESIGN

3.1 DATA DICTIONARY

Database jsp_graphical_password

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
accnumber	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
name	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
pass	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
deposit	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
rdate	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
report	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
status	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
balance	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL

3.2 TABLE DESIGN

Dumping data for table amount

1	123123	arun	123	0	19-11-2019	0	0	800
2	123	sham	123	0	19-11-2019	0	0	600

Table structure for table mini

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	int(10)	Yes	NULL
name	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
accnumber	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
evnt	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
amount	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
trans_to	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
rdate	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
report	varchar(35)	Yes	NULL
publickey	varchar(50)	Yes	NULL
privatekey	varchar(50)	Yes	NULL

Dumping data for table mini

1	arun	123123	trans_to	100	123	20-11-2019	1		
2	sham	123	trans_from	100	123123	20-11-2019	0	0	0

Table structure for table user_reg

Field	Type	Null	Default
id	int(20)	Yes	NULL
name	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
contact	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
email	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
accno	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
cardno	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
date	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
bank	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
branch	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
address	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
uname	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
pass	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
cdate	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
x1	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
y1	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

x2	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
y2	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
x3	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
y3	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
image	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
status	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
report	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
pub_key	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL
priv_key	varchar(100)	Yes	NULL

Dumping data for table user_reg

1	arun	73393 33830	arunextazee@gmail.com	123 123	987654321 0123456	20-01-01	sbi	trichy	trichy	arun	11-23	19-11-2019	129	14	13	12	13	13	13	8	9870	80
2	sham	73393 33830	sham@gmail.com	123	987654321 0123456	20-11-28	sbi	trichy	trichy	sham	11-23	19-11-2019	21	22	21	20	25	21	1	1	9870	9870

3.3 RELATIONSHIP DIAGRAM

An entity–relationship model (ER model for short) describes interrelated things of interest in a specific domain of knowledge. A basic ER model is composed of entity types (which classify the things of interest) and specifies relationships that can exist between entities (instances of those entity types). In software_engineering, an ER model is commonly formed to represent things a business needs to remember in order to perform business processes. Consequently, the ER model becomes an abstract data_model, that defines a data or information structure which can be implemented in a database, typically a relational_database

Fig 3.3.3erdiagram

CHAPTER 4

PROGRAM DESIGN

4.1 MODULE DESCRIPTIONS

4.1.1 USER REGISTRATION

User has to register with the username, password and other details. Then, it is followed by selection of image from the list of five details. Select three points on the selected image. Then, click register button. The entered details will be saved in a server.

4.1.2 USER LOGIN WITH PASSWORD

User has to login with the username first. Then the user has to choose either the password method or the graphical password method. Select the password method. Enter the password. An OTP will be sent to the registered mail. Enter the OTP and click submit button. User's homepage will be displayed.

4.1.3 USER LOGIN WITH IMAGE

User has to login with the username first. Then the user has to choose either the password method or the graphical password method. Select the graphical password method. Select the correct image from the list of five images. Select the three points and click submit button. User's homepage will be displayed.

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM TESTING

5.1.1 UNIT TESTING

The first test in the development process is the unit test. The source code is normally divided into modules, which in turn are divided into smaller units called units. These units have specific behavior. The test done on these units of code is called unit test. Unit test depends upon the language on which the project is developed.

Unit tests ensure that each unique path of the project performs accurately to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs and expected results. Functional and reliability testing in an Engineering environment. Producing tests for the behavior of components (nodes and vertices) of a product to ensure their correct behavior prior to system integration.

In this testing, user registration is done and checked for errors. User registration is done successfully.

5.1.2 INTEGRATION TESTING

Testing is which modules are combined and tested as a group. Modules are typically code modules, individual applications, source and destination applications on a network, etc. Integration Testing follows unit testing and precedes system testing. Testing after the product is code complete. Betas are often widely distributed or even distributed to the public at large in hopes that they will buy the final product when it is release.

In this testing, user login is checked. When user enters all the details correctly, user home will be displayed.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

User authentication is a fundamental component in most computer security contexts. In this extended abstract, proposed a simple graphical password authentication system. The system combines image selection and pixel selection concepts and forms as a single method. This method is more secured as pixel selection can't be identified easily. Computational cost and space complexity are less for the proposed method. As a future work, restrictions for image selection can be fixed. This provides complete security. The only limitation with graphical passwords is the slow mapping process as size of high quality images increases.

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47. Kamal Acharya. *Web chatting application project report management system*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.18588592/v1>
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CHAPTER 8

APPENDICES

8.1 – SOURCE CODE

```
<!doctype html>
<html>
<head>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-
8" />
<title>CC</title>
<link rel="stylesheet" href="styles.css" type="text/css" />
<!--[if lt IE 9]>
<script
src="http://html5shiv.googlecode.com/svn/trunk/html5.js"></scrip
t>
<![endif]-->
<!--
adage, a free CSS web template by ZyPOP (zypopwebtemplates.com/)
```

Download: <http://zypopwebtemplates.com/>

License: Creative Commons Attribution

```
//-->
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, minimum-
scale=1.0, maximum-scale=1.0" />
</head>
<body>
<div id="container" class="width">
```

```
<header>
```

```
    <h1><a href="">Credit<span> Card
Maintenance</span></a></h1>
```

```
</header>
```

```
<nav>
```

```
    <div class="inner-nav">
        <ul>
            <li class="start selected"><a
href="index.jsp">Home</a></li>
```

```

        <li class=""><a href="user.jsp">User</a></li>
        <li class=""><a href="admin.jsp">Admin</a></li>

    </ul>
</div>
</nav>

<div id="body">

    <section id="content">

        <article>
            <div class="article-info"><div align="right">
                <table width="200" border="0">
<tr>

<td><h2 align="center">Introduction to Secure Bank
Transaction</h2></td>
<td><div align="right"><imgsrc="images/medicalrecordscan-
logo.png" width="200" height="80"></div></td>
</tr>
</table>

                </div>
            </div>

        </article>

        <article class="expanded">
            <p align="justify"> A credit card is different from a
charge card, which requires the balance to be repaid in full
each month. In contrast, credit cards allow the consumers a
continuing balance of debt, subject to interest being charged. A
credit card also differs from a cash card, which can be used
like currency by the owner of the card. </p>

<h3>Secure Bank</h3>

<p align="justify">A bank is a financial institution that
accepts deposits from the public and creates credit. Lending
activities can be performed either directly or indirectly

```

through capital markets. Due to their importance in the financial stability of a country, banks are highly regulated in most countries. Most nations have institutionalized a system known as fractional reserve banking under which banks hold liquid assets equal to only a portion of their current liabilities.</p>

```
</article>
</section>

<aside class="sidebar">

<ul>
<li>
<h4><span>Categories</span></h4>
<ul>
<li><a href="index.jsp">Home Page</a></li>
<li><a href="user_reg.jsp">User
Registration</a></li>
<li><a href="user.jsp">User Login</a></li>
<li><a href="admin.jsp">Admin Login</a></li>
</ul>
</li>

<li>
<h4><span>About us</span></h4>
<ul>
<li class="text">
<div align="justify">Elliptic-curve cryptography (ECC) is an
approach to public-key cryptography based on the algebraic
structure of elliptic curves over finite fields.
<p style="margin: 0;">&nbsp;</p>
</div>
</li>
</ul>
</li>

<li></li>
<li>
<h4><span>Helpful Links</span></h4>
<ul>
<li><a href="index.jsp" title="premium
templates">Home</a></li>
```

```

<li><a href="about.jsp" title="web hosting">About As</a></li>
      <li><a href="contact.jsp"
title="premium templates">Contact As</a></li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</aside>
      <div class="clear"></div>
</div>
<footer>
<div class="footer-bottom">
<p>&copy; YourSite 2019. <a href="index.jsp">CCM</a></p>
</div>
</footer>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

```

<%
try
{
session.removeAttribute("username");
session.removeAttribute("name");
session.removeAttribute("pu_key");
session.removeAttribute("pri_key");
session.removeAttribute("dest");
response.sendRedirect("index.jsp");
}
catch(Exception e)
{
}
%>

```

```

<%@include file="include/dbconnect.jsp" %>

```

```

<%
String sid=(String)session.getAttribute("id");
String imgid="1";
String cid=request.getParameter("id");
//out.print(sid);
//stmt1.executeUpdate("update user_reg set image='"+cid+"' where
id='"+sid+"'");
//response.sendRedirect("user_reg_3.jsp");
%>

```



```

document.getElementById("x").innerHTML = PosX;
document.getElementById("y").innerHTML = PosY;
}

//-->
</script>
</head>
<body>


<script type="text/javascript">
<!--
varmyImg = document.getElementById("myImgId");
myImg.onmousedown = GetCoordinates;
//-->
</script>

<imgsrc="red.gif" width="400" height="300" alt="" id="myImgId"
/>
<p>X:<span id="x"></span></p>
<p>Y:<span id="y"></span></p></body>
</html>

<%@ include file="include/dbconnect.jsp" %>
<%@page import="java.util.Random"%>
<%@page import="java.sql.ResultSet"%>

<%

try
{
String a=request.getParameter("btn");
if(a.equals("Submit"))
{
String name=request.getParameter("uname");
String pass=request.getParameter("pass");
out.print(name+" "+pass);
String qry="select * from user_reg where uname='"+name+"' &&
pass='"+pass+"' ";
// out.print(qry);
ResultSetrs=stmt.executeQuery(qry);
if(rs.next())
{
String sid=rs.getString("id");
String img=rs.getString("image");
String x1=rs.getString("x1");

```

```

        String y1=rs.getString("y1");
        String x2=rs.getString("x2");
        String y2=rs.getString("y2");
        String x3=rs.getString("x3");
        String y3=rs.getString("y3");
        String accno=rs.getString("accno");
    session.setAttribute("accno",accno);
    session.setAttribute("sid",sid);
    session.setAttribute("img",img);
    session.setAttribute("uname",name);
    session.setAttribute("x1",x1);
session.setAttribute("y1",y1);
session.setAttribute("x2",x2);
session.setAttribute("y2",y2);
session.setAttribute("x3",x3);
session.setAttribute("y3",y3);
session.setAttribute("res",""+0);
session.setAttribute("imgid",""+1);

        response.sendRedirect("user_1.jsp");
    }
    else
    {
%>
                <script language="javascript">
                    alert("user name/ pass Rong!");
window.location="user.jsp";
                </script>

                <%

                    }

                rs.close();

    }

}catch (Exception e)
{

//out.print(e);

```

```
}
```

```
%>
```

```
<%@page contentType="text/html" pageEncoding="UTF-8"%>
```

```
<!doctype html>
```

```
<html>
```

```
<head>
```

```
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
```

```
<title>CC</title>
```

```
<link rel="stylesheet" href="styles.css" type="text/css" />
```

```
<!--[if lt IE 9]>
```

```
<script
```

```
src="http://html5shiv.googlecode.com/svn/trunk/html5.js"></scrip  
t>
```

```
<![endif]-->
```

```
<!--
```

```
adage, a free CSS web template by ZyPOP (zypopwebtemplates.com/)
```

```
Download: http://zypopwebtemplates.com/
```

```
License: Creative Commons Attribution
```

```
//-->
```

```
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, minimum-  
scale=1.0, maximum-scale=1.0" />
```

```
<style type="text/css">
```

```
<!--
```

```
.style2 {color: #2E6290; font-weight: bold; }
```

```
.style3 {
```

```
    color: #FA8B37;
```

```
    font-weight: bold;
```

```
}
```

```
-->
```

```
</style>
```

```
</head>
```

```
<body>
```

```
<div id="container" class="width">
```

```
<header>
```

```
    <h1><a href="">Credit<span> Card  
Maintenance</span></a></h1>
```

```
</header>
```

```

<nav>
  <div class="inner-nav">
    <ul>
      <li class="start selected"><a
href="index.jsp">Home</a></li>
      <li class="start selected"><a
href="user.jsp">User</a></li>
      <li class=""><a href="admin.jsp">Admin</a></li>
    </ul>
  </div>
</nav>

<div id="body">

  <section id="content">

    <article>
      <div class="article-info"><div align="right">
        <table width="200" border="0">
<tr>
<td><h2 align="center">User Login </h2></td>
<td><div align="right"><imgsrc="images/user-512.png" width="152"
height="80"></div></td>
</tr>
</table>
      </div>
    </div>
  </article>

  <article class="expanded">
    <form name="form1" method="post" action="">
      <table width="60%" border="0">
<tr>
<td width="23%">&nbsp;</td>
<td width="57%"><table width="61%" border="0" align="center">
<tr>
<td width="35%" class="tdsh"><div align="center" class="style2">

```

```
<div align="right">User name </div>
```

```

</div></td>
<td width="8%" class="tdsh"><div align="center"
class="style2">:</div></td>
<td width="57%" class="tdsh"><label>
<input name="uname" type="text" id="uname">
</label></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="tdsh"><div align="center" class="style2">
<div align="right">Password</div>
</div></td>
<td class="tdsh"><div align="center" class="style2">:</div></td>
<td class="tdsh"><label>
<input name="pass" type="password" id="pass">
</label></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="tdsh">&nbsp;</td>
<td colspan="2" class="tdsh"><label>
<input name="btn" type="submit" class="btnclr" id="btn"
value="Submit">
<span class="style3"><a href="user_reg.jsp">New
user...</a></span></label></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
<td width="20%">&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
</table>
</form>
<p align="justify">&nbsp;</p>
</article>
</section>

<aside class="sidebar">

<ul>
<li>
<h4><span>Categories</span></h4>
<ul>
<li><a href="index.jsp">Home Page</a></li>
<li><a href="user_reg.jsp">User
Registration</a></li>
<li><a href="user.jsp">User Login</a></li>
<li><a href="admin.jsp">Admin Login</a></li>
</ul>
</li>

```

```

<li>
<h4><span>Helpful Links</span></h4>
</li>

<li><ul>
                                <li><a href="index.jsp" title="premium
templates">Home</a></li>

<li><a href="about.jsp" title="web hosting">About As</a></li>
                                <li><a href="contact.jsp"
title="premium templates">Contact As</a></li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</aside>
    <div class="clear"></div>
</div>
<footer>
<div class="footer-bottom">
<p>&copy; YourSite 2019. <a href="index.jsp">CCM</a></p>
</div>
</footer>
</div>
</body>
</html>
<%@page import="java.util.Random"%>
<%@ include file="include/dbconnect.jsp" %>

<%
String sid=(String)session.getAttribute("sid");

    %>

<!doctype html>
<html>
<head>
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=utf-
8" />
<title>CC</title>
<link rel="stylesheet" href="styles.css" type="text/css" />
<!--[if lt IE 9]>
<script
src="http://html5shiv.googlecode.com/svn/trunk/html5.js"></scrip
t>
<![endif]-->
<!--

```

adage, a free CSS web template by ZyPOP (zypopwebtemplates.com/)

Download: <http://zypopwebtemplates.com/>

License: Creative Commons Attribution

```
//-->
```

```
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, minimum-  
scale=1.0, maximum-scale=1.0" />
```

```
<style type="text/css">
```

```
<!--
```

```
.style1 {color: #2E6290}
```

```
.style2 {font-weight: bold}
```

```
-->
```

```
</style>
```

```
<script language="javascript">
```

```
function validate()
```

```
{
```

```
    // alert("");
```

```
if (document.form1.name.value == "")
```

```
{
```

```
    alert("Enter the Name");
```

```
    document.form1.name.focus();
```

```
    return false;
```

```
}
```

```
if (document.form1.cont.value == "")
```

```
{
```

```
    alert("Enter the Contact");
```

```
    document.form1.cont.focus();
```

```
    return false;
```

```
}
```

```
if (document.form1.cont.value != "")
```

```
{
```

```
    var z = document.form1.cont.value;
```

```
    if(!/^[0-9]+$/.test(z)){
```

```
        alert("enter 0-9")
```

```
        document.form1.cont.focus();
```

```
        return false;
```

```
    }
```

```
}
```

```
if (document.form1.cont.value != "")
```

```
{
```

```
    var a=document.form1.cont.value;
```

```
    if(!(a.length ==10)) //i got a problem with this one i think
```

```
{
```

```

alert("Enter 10 character length");
document.form1.cont.focus();

return false;
}

}

if (document.form1.email.value == "")
{
alert("Enter the email");
document.form1.email.focus();
return false;
}
if (document.form1.email.value != "")
{
varmailformat = /^\\w+([\\.-]?\\w+)*@\\w+([\\.-]?\\w+)*\\.\\w{2,3}+$/;
if(document.form1.email.value.match(mailformat))
{
}
else
{
alert("You have entered an invalid email address!");
document.form1.email.focus();
return false;
}
}

if (document.form1.address.value == "")
{
alert("Enter the address");
document.form1.address.focus();
return false;
}

if (document.form1.uname.value == "")
{
alert("Enter the uname");
document.form1.uname.focus();
return false;
}

if (document.form1.pass.value == "")
{
alert("Enter the pass");
document.form1.pass.focus();
return false;
}if (document.form1.cpass.value == "")
{

```

```

alert("Enter the conform pass");
document.form1.cpass.focus();
return false;
    }

    //finishMD();
return true;
    }
</script>
</head>
<body>
<div id="container" class="width">

<header>

    <h1><a href="">Credit<span> Card
Maintenance</span></a></h1>

</header>

<nav>
    <div class="inner-nav">
        <ul>
            <li class="start selected"><a
href="index.jsp">Home</a></li>
            <li class="start selected"><a
href="user.jsp">User</a></li>

            <li class=""><a href="admin.jsp">Admin</a></li>

            <li class=""><a href="about.jsp">About As</a></li>

            <li class=""><a href="contact.jsp">Contact</a></li>

        </ul>
    </div>
</nav>

<div id="body">

    <section id="content">

```

```

    <article>
    <div class="article-info"><div align="right">
        <table width="200" border="0">
<tr>

<td><h2 align="center">User Login </h2></td>
<td><div align="right"><imgsrc="images/user-512.png" width="152"
height="80"></div></td>
</tr>
</table>
        </div>
    </div>
</article>

    <article class="expanded">
    <form name="form1" method="post" action="">
    <table width="60%" border="0">
<tr>

<td width="16%">&nbsp;</td>
<td width="64%"><table width="597" height="263" border="0"
align="center">
<tr>
<td><a href="user_2.jsp?id=1"><imgsrc="img/1.png" width="100"
height="100"></a></td>
<td><a href="user_2.jsp?id=2"><imgsrc="img/2.png" width="100"
height="100"></a></td>
<td><a href="user_2.jsp?id=3"><imgsrc="img/3.png" width="100"
height="100"></a></td>
<td><a href="user_2.jsp?id=4"><imgsrc="img/4.png" width="100"
height="100"></a></td>
<td><a href="user_2.jsp?id=5"><imgsrc="img/5.png" width="100"
height="100"></a></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<td class="tdsh"><a href="user_2.jsp?id=6"><imgsrc="img/6.png"
width="100" height="100"></a></td>
<td class="tdsh"><a href="user_2.jsp?id=7"><imgsrc="img/7.png"
width="100" height="100"></a></td>
<td class="tdsh"><a href="user_2.jsp?id=8"><imgsrc="img/8.png"
width="100" height="100"></a></td>
<td class="tdsh"><a href="user_2.jsp?id=9"><imgsrc="img/9.png"
width="100" height="100"></a></td>
<td class="tdsh"><a href="user_2.jsp?id=10"><imgsrc="img/10.png"
width="100" height="100"></a></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
<td width="20%">&nbsp;</td>

```

</tr>

```

</table>
</form>
    <p align="justify">&nbsp;  </p>
</article>
</section>

<aside class="sidebar">

<ul>
<li>
<h4><span>Categories</span></h4>
<ul>
<li><a href="index.jsp">Home Page</a></li>
    <li><a href="user_reg.jsp">User
Registration</a></li>
<li><a href="user.jsp">User Login</a></li>
<li><a href="admin.jsp">Admin Login</a></li>
</ul>
</li>

<li>
<h4><span>Helpful Links</span></h4>
</li>
<li><ul>
    <li><a href="index.jsp" title="premium
templates">Home</a></li>

<li><a href="about.jsp" title="web hosting">About As</a></li>
    <li><a href="contact.jsp"
title="premium templates">Contact As</a></li>
</ul>
</li>
</ul>
</aside>
    <div class="clear"></div>
</div>
<footer>
<div class="footer-bottom">
<p>&copy; YourSite 2019. <a href="index.jsp">CCM</a></p>
</div>
</footer>
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

8.2 _O/P SCREENS

credit card maintenance

home user admin

Categories

- Home Page
- User Registration
- User Login
- Admin Login

About us

Elliptic-curve cryptography (ECC) is an approach to public-key cryptography based on the algebraic structure of elliptic curves over finite fields.

Helpful Links

- Home
- About As

Categories

- Home Page
- User Registration
- User Login
- Admin Login

Helpful Links

- Home
- About As
- Contact As

Introduction to Secure Bank Transaction

A credit card is different from a charge card, which requires the balance to be repaid in full each month. In contrast, credit cards allow the consumers a continuing balance of debt, subject to interest being charged. A credit card also differs from a cash card, which can be used like currency by the owner of the card.

Secure Bank

A bank is a financial institution that accepts deposits from the public and creates credit. Lending activities can be performed either directly or indirectly through capital markets. Due to their importance in the financial stability of a country, banks are highly regulated in most countries. Most nations have institutionalized a system known as fractional reserve banking under which banks hold liquid assets equal to only a portion of their current liabilities.

User Registration

Name :

Contact :

Email :

Account Number :

Card Number :

Expiry date :

Bank :

Branch :

Address :

User Name :

Password :

C-Password :

credit card maintenance

[home](#) [user](#) [admin](#)

Categories

[Home Page](#)
[User Registration](#)
[User Login](#)
[Admin Login](#)

Helpful Links

[Home](#)
[About As](#)
[Contact As](#)

User Login

User name :

Password :

[New user...](#)

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User Registration

X:275

Y:202

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X:270

Y:198

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X:268

Y:197

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Welcome akila

The address bar turns green indicating that the site is secured with an SSL Certificate that meets the Extended Validation Standard.

Banking

Available balance

10000

Id	Event	Amount	ACC_number	Date
1	deposit	15000	-	23-11-2019
2	withdraw	5000	-	23-11-2019

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Welcome akila

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Banking

Available balance

10000

Deposit Amount

Submit

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Welcome akila

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Banking

Available balance

12000

Withdraw Amount

Submit

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Welcome akila

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Transaction

Transaction

11500

Account Number

Trans Amount

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User name :

Password :

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